

MALE SEX GLANDS

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Annotation: *Anatomical, physiological, histological structure of the male reproductive system. Protection of the genitalia from the external environment and the factors that cause it. Problems of the male reproductive system and measures to prevent it. Related functions of the excretion system and the reproductive system. Sexual system diseases.*

Keywords: *Penis, testicle, disease, sexual weakness*

Content of the article: Male genitalia (organa genitalia masculine) are the most important and vital organs in human life. These organs are called genital organs in medicine. According to the morphological structure of the genital organs, they are divided into two groups: internal and external. The external genitalia consists of the penis, the scrotum. Internal genital organs: testis and epididimes, sexual glands. The specificity, that the common to both systems - the male excretion system, the urinary tract - and are studied together.

The development of the sexual glands of the male reproductive system begins with the penetration of the sexual systems - the sexually transmitted systems located above the primary kidney. In the early stages of development of epithelial systems, they are radially oriented, and then begin to grow. They begin to form curves, and from this time on, the curves are called curry seed ridges. At first, these are morphologically identical, and then they gradually decompose. By 4 months of pregnancy, cavity of curved channels begins to develop. In the last months of embryonic development, the male sex glands do not change much, only after the birth of the child and adulthood are complex changes in the spermatogonia and the reproductive cells begin to mature.

The testis is a member of a group of dual organs in the human body and is located in the scrotum. It has an oval shape and has internal - facies medialis, external - facies lateralis surfaces. It also has front and rear edges. The left testicle is slightly below the right. At the back of the testis, seed systems begins, and in this area, the testis consists of the epididymis, its head, the lower tail, and the body part

between them. The testis is surrounded by a seventh layer of protective veil, which protects the testis from external influences.

The penis - belongs to the external group of male genitalia..

The root of the penis is the radix penis

Male penis head is glans penis

Penis body - corpus penis

Feet - crus penis

Consist of parts, in the middle of the head there is the urinary tract, the excretory part, and the seed path is also opened.

The body of the penis is composed of porous structures, which, as a consequence of their filling with blood, change the size and tension of the penis.

Many sexually infectious diseases can be transmitted through male genitalia. We can cite many diseases of the genitals. These are:

syphilis, chlamydia, gonorrhoea, trichomoniasis, mycoplasmas, ureplasmosis, genital herpes, pedicule (genital mite) and infertility.

These diseases can destroy a person's life. One of the problems that afflicts so many men today is sexual weakness. Sexual weakness can be explained by early termination (relaxation), impotence or erection disorders during sexual intercourse. The reasons for this are first explored. In these cases, different drugs are treated. Infertility is also due to the loss of fertility. There are several reasons for this;

mechanical impact, various infectious diseases, varicocele, defects of genital development.

If the causes of infertility are identified early on, the chances of it being treated are even higher. Everyone should care about their health, let's take care of health!

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